

Supplementary Materials - Study Protocol

For

On Simulation-Guided LLM-based Code Generation for Safe Autonomous Driving

Step 1: The experts are selected from a pool of experts who involved in different aspects of AD and ADAS functions developments in OEMs.

Step 2: They are asked the following questions, and their answers are collected.

Your information

1. Participant ID

2. Which area are you working in?

- Automotive- Autonomous Vehicles or ADAS Functions
- Automotive- Other safety relevant applications
- Automotive- Non safety relevant functions
- Other

3. Which one is true about your company:

- OEM
- Software supplier
- Other

4. Please specify your role:

- Manager or Product Owner
- Software Developer
- System or Function Developer
- Verification and Validation Engineer
- Safety Engineer
- Other

5. Which case is true in your case:

- Writing Codes
- Reviewing Codes
- Providing inputs to the programmers (E.g., requirements, software architectures, ...)
- Receiver of softwares (e.g., Testing, integration of software with other components, ...)
- Other

6. How long have you been working in this role and in automotive domain (including relevant PhD years)?

Next

Your experience with code generation using

7. Do you have any experience with using Large Language Models for code generation?

Yes

No

8. If yes which Model?

Enter your answer

9. **Strength/Weakness, and Advantages/Disadvantages:**

Can you share your thoughts on code generation using LLMs, including any strength/weakness, and advantages/disadvantages you perceive?

Enter your answer

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Challenges in Automated Code Generation vs. Human Generated Code

To what extent do you agree or disagree with the challenges in using LLM automated code generation? For each statement, you can select from strongly agree to strongly disagree. There is also a neutral option if you have no opinion or experience with that specific challenge or question. You can also use this option if you prefer not to answer that specific question. After each challenge, you can elaborate more on the reason for your choice and potential solutions or approaches (not mandatory).

10. **Understandability and Correctness Assessment:**

It is difficult to understand and assess the correctness of the LLM-generated code.

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree
- Agree
- Strongly Agree
- Neutral

11. Any comment?

Enter your answer

12. **Review and bug fixing Effort:**

Reviewing, bug-fixing, and modifying the generated code requires more time than human generated code.

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree
- Agree
- Strongly Agree
- Neutral

13. Any comment?

Enter your answer

14. Prompt Engineering Difficulties:

It is unknown/difficult to communicate with LLM and specify the requirements on the expected code.

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree
- Agree
- Strongly Agree
- Neutral

15. Any comment?

Enter your answer

16. Unnecessary complexity of Generated code:

The generated code by LLM is unnecessarily more complex than human generated code.

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree
- Agree
- Strongly Agree
- Neutral

17. Any comment?

Enter your answer

18. Domain-Specific terms:

Some Domain-Specific terms are not understood by the model.

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree
- Agree
- Strongly Agree
- Neutral

19. Any comment?

Enter your answer

20. Unpredictable Results:

It is hard/impossible to predict and control the code generated by LLMs.

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree
- Agree
- Strongly Agree
- Neutral

21. Any comment?

Enter your answer

22. Incorrect or inaccurate Code:

The generated code does not meet the functional or non-functional requirements, although they are provided in the prompt.

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree
- Agree
- Strongly Agree
- Neutral

23. Any comment?

Enter your answer

24. Insecure or unsafe Code:

The generated code violate safety or cyber-security requirements.

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree
- Agree
- Strongly Agree
- Neutral

25. Any comment?

Enter your answer

26. Violation of Confidentiality:

Providing requirements, codes to LLM violate confidentiality and exposing my or my company's intellectual property to a third party.

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree
- Agree
- Strongly Agree
- Neutral

27. Any comment?

Enter your answer

28. Unknown Code reference:

It is impossible/hard to find out if the code totally or partially is generated from existing code in the training data, and the reference to it.

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree
- Agree
- Strongly Agree
- Neutral

29. Any comment?

Enter your answer

30. **Legal, Copyright and Intellectual Property Infringement:**

The generated code might include the intellectual property of a third party.

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree
- Agree
- Strongly Agree
- Neutral

31. Any comment?

Enter your answer

32. **Not suitable for complex Software:**

The model can not handle or generate correct code for complex algorithms.

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree
- Agree
- Strongly Agree
- Neutral

33. Any comment?

Enter your answer

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Step 3: Then the tool is demoed to them. The following are some screenshots from the recorded Demo:

The first version of developed code:

```

1
2 class CustomController:
3     def __init__(self, state):
4         self.state = state
5
6     def stop(self):
7         ego = self.state.vehicles[0]
8         vehicles_ahead = [v for v in self.state.vehicles if v.lane_id == ego.lane_id and v.s > ego.s]
9
10        closest_vehicle, ttc = self.find_closest_vehicle_and_ttc(ego, vehicles_ahead)
11
12        # Check if collision is imminent based on ttc threshold (e.g. 5 seconds)
13        if closest_vehicle and ttc < 5.0:
14            self.execute_evasive_maneuver(ego, vehicles_ahead)
15
16    def find_closest_vehicle_and_ttc(self, ego, vehicles):
17        closest_vehicle = None
18        min_ttc = float('inf')
19
20        for vehicle in vehicles:
21            distance = vehicle.s - ego.s - 4 # Assume max length of vehicle is 4 meters
22            relative_velocity = ego.speed - vehicle.speed
23            heading_difference = abs(ego.heading - vehicle.heading)
24
25            if relative_velocity > 0:
26                ttc = (distance / relative_velocity) / heading_difference
27                if ttc < min_ttc:
28                    min_ttc = ttc
29                    closest_vehicle = vehicle
30
31        return closest_vehicle, min_ttc
32
33    def execute_evasive_maneuver(self, ego, vehicles_ahead):
34        # Ranking potential lanes: preference to the left if possible
35        potential_lanes = [ego.lane_id - 1 if ego.lane_id > -4 else None,
36                          ego.lane_id + 1 if ego.lane_id < -2 else None]
37
38        for lane_id in potential_lanes:
39            if lane_id and self.is_lane_change_safe(ego, lane_id):
40                self.state.switch_lane(lane_id - ego.lane_id) # -1 for left, +1 for right
41                break
42
43    def is_lane_change_safe(self, ego, target_lane_id):
44        vehicles_in_target_lane = [v for v in self.state.vehicles if v.lane_id == target_lane_id]
45        vehicles_ahead_in_target_lane = [v for v in vehicles_in_target_lane if v.s > ego.s]
46
47        if not vehicles_ahead_in_target_lane:
48            return True # Lane is clear
  
```

Its simulation:

The generated report:

```
2024-04-28_11-42-30_CAEM.txt
1 Static code analysis for iteration 0:
2 task: CAEM, new controller: True, vision: True
3 code_analysis: {'average_complexity': 4.6, 'maintainability_score': 68.09279320498271, 'maintainability_grade': 'A', 'code_density': 0.666377358490566}
4 pep8_analysis: {'errors': 0, 'warnings': 20}
5 pep8_issues: {'errors': [], 'warnings': ['custom_controller.py:5:1: W293 blank line contains whitespace', 'custom_controller.py:8:80: E501 line too long (101 > 79 characters)', 'custo
6   tom_controller.py:9:1: W293 blank line contains whitespace', 'custom_controller.py:10:80: E501 line too long (85 > 79 characters)', 'custom_controller.py:11:1: W293 blank line contai
7   ns whitespace', 'custom_controller.py:12:80: E501 line too long (80 > 79 characters)', 'custom_controller.py:15:1: W293 blank line contains whitespace', 'custom_controller.py:19:1:
8   W293 blank line contains whitespace', 'custom_controller.py:21:80: E501 line too long (88 > 79 characters)', 'custom_controller.py:24:1: W293 blank line contains whitespace', 'custi
9   om_controller.py:30:1: W293 blank line contains whitespace', 'custom_controller.py:32:1: W293 blank line contains whitespace', 'custom_controller.py:35:74: W291 trailing whitespace':
10  , 'custom_controller.py:37:1: W293 blank line contains whitespace', 'custom_controller.py:40:80: E501 line too long (90 > 79 characters)', 'custom_controller.py:44:80: E501 line tooo
11  long (97 > 79 characters)', 'custom_controller.py:45:80: E501 line too long (91 > 79 characters)', 'custom_controller.py:49:1: W293 blank line contains whitespace', 'custom_control
12  ler.py:50:80: E501 line too long (86 > 79 characters)', 'custom_controller.py:51:80: E501 line too long (84 > 79 characters)']}
13
14 Iteration 0 reports:
15 Log based report for scenario: cut-in_high.xosc:
16 Fail: Ego was involved in a collision at time: 13.1 s with a speed of 33.333333 m/s, colliding with: OverTaker.
17 Fail: Closest distance Ego comes to any vehicle is 0.98 m to vehicle #2 at time: 13.5 s, which is closer than the allowed minimum of 7 m.
18 Fail: Greatest absolute lane offset of Ego: 11.70 m at time: 16.2 s, which exceeds the allowed maximum of 9.7 m
19 Pass: Smallest absolute lane offset of Ego: 8.00 m at time: 0.0 s, above the allowed minimum of 3.425 m
20
21 Vision based report for scenario: cut-in_high.xosc:
22 In the first image, Ego (the white car) and OverTaker (the red car) are traveling in adjacent lanes on a multi-lane highway. Ego is maintaining a speed of 120.0 km/h in the lane secti
23   ond from the right, while OverTaker is in the leftmost lane traveling slightly slower at 84.96 km/h. The distance traveled by Ego is exactly 400.00 meters, and OverTaker has traveled
24   d 442.16 meters. There are no visible signs of a lane change or overlap in the paths of the vehicles at this point.
25
26 In the second image, both vehicles have come closer to each other, and OverTaker seems to have decelerated to a speed of 70.56 km/h while still remaining in the leftmost lane. Ego co
27   ntinues to travel at a consistent speed of 120.0 km/h. The lines on the ground indicate that Ego has continued along a straight path without changing lanes, but OverTaker's line indi
28   cates a slight trajectory suggesting a potential move to the right, towards Ego's lane.
29
30 The third image shows a direct overlap of OverTaker and Ego's paths, indicating a collision scenario. OverTaker has maneuvered into Ego's lane, as evidenced by their trailing line
31   s merging. At the time of the collision, OverTaker is decelerating further to 56.16 km/h, and Ego maintains a constant speed of 120.0 km/h. The overlapping paths and disparity in si
32   speeds suggest that OverTaker may have changed lanes into Ego's path without sufficient clearance, resulting in Ego colliding with OverTaker. Both cars are still in the second lane
33   e from the right, as indicated by the road markings and trailing lines.
34
35 Based on the information provided and the movement pattern leading to the collision, it appears that OverTaker's lane change in front of Ego, coupled with its deceleration, led to th
36   e collision with Ego, who maintained a consistent speed and did not alter its course to avoid the encroaching vehicle.
37
38 Log based report for scenario: cut-in_middle.xosc:
39 Fail: Ego was involved in a collision at time: 13.5 s with a speed of 22.222222 m/s, colliding with: OverTaker.
40 Fail: Closest distance Ego comes to any vehicle is 1.12 m to vehicle #2 at time: 14.0 s, which is closer than the allowed minimum of 7 m.
41 Pass: Greatest absolute lane offset of Ego: 11.70 m at time: 16.7 s, within the allowed maximum of 9.7 m
42 Pass: Smallest absolute lane offset of Ego: 8.00 m at time: 0.0 s, above the allowed minimum of 3.425 m
43
44 Vision based report for scenario: cut-in_middle.xosc:
45 Based on the sequence of images provided, here is what appears to have occurred:
46
47 In the first image, we see two vehicles on a multi-lane highway. Ego, the white vehicle, is maintaining a steady speed of 80.00 km/h and is positioned on the rightmost lane, as indi
48   cated by 'lane -3/0' which suggests it is in lane 3 with no ongoing lane change. The red vehicle, labeled OverTaker, has a higher speed of 49.92 km/h and is overtaking Ego from the
49   1(005)-- 2024-04-28_11-42-30_CAEM.txt (1,0) (Text) 12:35 - 04 July 2024 3.43
```

The code from the second iteration:

```
1
2 class CustomController:
3     def __init__(self, state):
4         self.state = state
5
6     def step(self):
7         ego = self.state.vehicles[0]
8         vehicles_ahead = [v for v in self.state.vehicles if v.lane_id == ego.lane_id and v.s > ego.s]
9
10        closest_vehicle, ttc = self.find_closest_vehicle_and_ttc(ego, vehicles_ahead)
11
12        # Check if collision is imminent based on ttc threshold (e.g. 5 seconds)
13        if closest_vehicle and ttc < 5.0:
14            self.execute_evasive_maneuver(ego, vehicles_ahead)
15
16        def find_closest_vehicle_and_ttc(self, ego, vehicles):
17            closest_vehicle = None
18            min_ttc = float('inf')
19
20            for vehicle in vehicles:
21                distance = vehicle.s - ego.s - 4 # Assume max length of vehicle is 4 meters
22                relative_velocity = ego.speed - vehicle.speed
23                heading_difference = abs(ego.heading - vehicle.heading)
24
25                if relative_velocity > 0:
26                    ttc = (distance / relative_velocity) / heading_difference
27                    if ttc < min_ttc:
28                        min_ttc = ttc
29                        closest_vehicle = vehicle
30
31            return closest_vehicle, min_ttc
32
33        def execute_evasive_maneuver(self, ego, vehicles_ahead):
34            # Ranking potential lanes: preference to the left if possible
35            potential_lanes = [ego.lane_id - 1 if ego.lane_id > -4 else None,
36                              ego.lane_id + 1 if ego.lane_id < -2 else None]
37
38            for lane_id in potential_lanes:
39                if lane_id and self.is_lane_change_safe(ego, lane_id):
40                    self.state.switch_lane(lane_id - ego.lane_id) # -1 for left, +1 for right
41                    break
42
43
44----- 0_custom_controller.py (2, 0) (Python Flymake[0 0]) [eglot:controller] 12:34 - 04 July 2024 1.83
45(1/1) Find files: ~/Downloads/all_data (1)/root/vision/Implementation/CAEM/2024-04-28_11-36-42_CAEM/controller/2_custom_controller.py
462_custom_controller.py
```

Its simulation:

Its generated Report:

```
157 Iteration 2 reports:
158 Log based report for scenario: cut-in_high.asec:
159 Pass: No collisions were detected.
160 Pass: Closest distance Ego comes to any vehicle is 24.27 m to vehicle #2 at time: 8.8 s, respecting the minimum allowed distance of 7 m.
161 Fail: Greatest absolute Lane offset of Ego: 11.70 m at time: 11.1 s, which exceeds the allowed maximum of 9.7 m.
162 Pass: Smallest absolute Lane offset of Ego: 8.80 m at time: 8.8 s, above the allowed minimum of 3.425 m.
163
164 Log based report for scenario: cut-in_middle.asec:
165 Pass: No collisions were detected.
166 Pass: Closest distance Ego comes to any vehicle is 16.26 m to vehicle #2 at time: 9.9 s, respecting the minimum allowed distance of 7 m.
167 Pass: Greatest absolute Lane offset of Ego: 11.70 m at time: 11.9 s, within the allowed maximum of 9.7 m.
168 Pass: Smallest absolute Lane offset of Ego: 8.80 m at time: 8.8 s, above the allowed minimum of 3.425 m.
169
170 Log based report for scenario: cut-in_low.asec:
171 Pass: No collisions were detected.
172 Pass: Closest distance Ego comes to any vehicle is 7.99 m to vehicle #2 at time: 15.5 s, respecting the minimum allowed distance of 7 m.
173 Fail: Greatest absolute Lane offset of Ego: 11.70 m at time: 18.8 s, which exceeds the allowed maximum of 9.7 m.
174 Pass: Smallest absolute Lane offset of Ego: 8.80 m at time: 8.8 s, above the allowed minimum of 3.425 m.
175
176 Log based report for scenario: cut-in_double_fm.asec:
177 Pass: No collisions were detected.
178 Pass: Closest distance Ego comes to any vehicle is 21.74 m to vehicle #2 at time: 8.4 s, respecting the minimum allowed distance of 7 m.
179 Fail: Greatest absolute Lane offset of Ego: 11.70 m at time: 11.5 s, which exceeds the allowed maximum of 9.7 m.
180 Pass: Smallest absolute Lane offset of Ego: 8.80 m at time: 8.8 s, above the allowed minimum of 3.425 m.
181
182 Log based report for scenario: cut-in_block_fm.asec:
183 Pass: No collisions were detected.
184 Pass: Closest distance Ego comes to any vehicle is 22.14 m to vehicle #2 at time: 6.8 s, respecting the minimum allowed distance of 7 m.
```

Step 4: and follow up questions are asked from them:

Demo of the tool and results from the tool:

In this section a recorded demo of the prototype of the tool and a sample results will be shown to you, then some follow up questions are asked.

34. To what extent do you find this tool useful?

- Very useful
- Useful
- Not Useful
- Should not being used
- Neutral

35. **Strength/Weakness, and Advantages/Disadvantages:**

Can you share your thoughts on the usefulness of this tool, including any strength/weakness, and advantages/disadvantages you perceive?

Enter your answer

36. **Potential Improvements:**

What improvements or adjustments would you recommend for the LLM to better serve the needs of the teams involved in development of AD?

Enter your answer

37. **Any other Comment?**

Enter your answer

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